

CONDUCTIVITY ANALYSIS OF THE MODERN BRIDGE CONNECTING TWO PARTS OF BOBUR AVENUE IN ANDIJAN CITY

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Annotation

In this article, new factors and ways to eliminate them are shown as a result of the construction of a modern bridge connecting two parts of Babur avenue in Andijan city.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada Andijon shahrida Bobur shoh ko'chasining ikki qismini bog'laydigan zamonaviy ko'priknig qurilishi natijasida kelib chiquvchi yangi omillar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari ko'rsatilib o'tilgan.

Аннотация

В данной статье показаны новые факторы и пути их устранения в результате строительства современного моста, соединяющего две части проспекта Бабура в городе Андижан.

Key words: public transport, program, master plan, priority, road infrastructure, traffic, railway line, bridge, private transport, restriction, privilege signs.

Kalit so'zlar: jamoat transporti, dastur, bosh reja, ustuvorlik, yo'l infratuzilmasi, tirbandlik, temir yo'l liniyasi, ko'priknig, shaxsiy transport, cheklov, imtiyoz belgilar.

Ключевые слова: общественный транспорт, программа, генеральный план, приоритет, дорожная инфраструктура, движение, железнодорожная линия, мост, частный транспорт, ограничение, знаки льгот.

In recent years, large-scale works have been carried out to improve the provision of motor transport services to the population, expand the network of public transport routes and update the traffic structure with modern, environmentally friendly buses, and fundamentally update the public transport infrastructure. Together with this, it is aimed to fully satisfy the needs of the population for high-quality and convenient passenger transportation services, to introduce market principles in the sector, in particular, to create an attractive business environment for the private sector by improving the financing system

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and tariff policy. Based on this, PQ-59 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 16, 2023 "On measures to reform the public transport system" and by improving the road infrastructure and creating safe driving conditions on the roads In order to drastically reduce the number of accidents and deaths, including the full digitalization of the traffic management system and to ensure broad participation of the public in the work in this field, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Safe and Smooth Decisions on approving the "road" nationwide program were approved. [1,2]

These state programs include: development of the General Plan for the development of transport and road infrastructure of Andijan city, formation of a new network of public transport routes, full implementation of the automated fare payment system (ATTO) in public transport , improvement of the tariff system in Andijan city public transport, development of road transport infrastructure in order to ensure the priority of public transport, comprehensive improvement of road infrastructure, digitization of the traffic management system on highways, development and digitization of public transport, road traffic it is determined to strengthen campaign work on ensuring safety, to establish practical teaching of traffic rules to children, and to improve the system of training and retraining of drivers, as well as to strengthen control over the technical condition of motor vehicles.

One of the factors that directly affects public transport in the city is the Tashkent - Andijan railway line, which crosses the city center of Andijan. This railway line does not cross only Alisher Navoi Avenue. It intersects with all other highways. This affects the timetable of the city public transport and reduces the efficiency of its use (Fig. 1). [3,4]

On Babur Avenue, drivers engaged in passenger transportation are using alternative road sections (Fig. 2). That is, the drivers

Figure 1

Figure 2

engaged in the activity of passenger transportation are traveling a distance of more than 5 km. At the same time, the presence of a guarded railway section at the intersection of Sanoat street and Amir Temur Avenue causes traffic jams on the existing road sections.

- In order to ensure the priority of public transport in the city of Andijan, to carry out the development of road infrastructure facilities in parallel with the direction of public transport, two parts of this Babur Avenue, a 700-meter long modern bridge passing over the Andijan railway station being joined by a prick.

- Now, the bridge connecting the two parts of Babur Avenue serves to increase the efficiency of public transport by providing priority.

- As a result of the studies, it was found that the following problems will arise as a result of the handover of the modern bridge being built on Babur Avenue:

- One part of Babur Avenue is connected to HEI (Higher education institutions) and the other part is due to the New Market area, causing traffic jams in both parts by leaving vehicles on the side of the road.

- Insufficient temporary parking spaces for vehicles in existing sections

- Current existing alternative roads, as a result of the construction of a modern bridge, lead to the direct entry of streams into the New Market area, and create such factors as natural traffic jams. [5,6]

In order to prevent such problems, first of all, priority should be given to urban public transport in the existing parts, introduction of restrictions on private vehicles, use of preferential signs on some streets to allow cars to get out of existing traffic jams, parking of existing cars in the New Market area. that it is desirable to place their places further away and to organize special highways for buses.

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